

3D Network Modeling for THz-Enabled Ultra-Fast Dense Networks: A 6G Perspective

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Abstract—Terahertz (THz) communications are envisioned as a critical technology for 6G and enable ultra-fast dense networks with tiny cells. Implementing THz-enabled ultra-fast cells requires new techniques due to its three-dimensional (3D) nature. Stochastic Geometry is a tool that is widely used for network deployment, which provides tractability and feasibility. In this paper, we provide a summary of 3D network modeling for the THz system. We discuss the new 6G Ultra-cell scenario along with a potential 3D network architecture. Several recent developments on network modeling applying a stochastic geometry-based clustered process are also presented. We also discuss several potential network modeling techniques such as Poisson Voronoi (PV) tessellation, Thomas cluster process (TCP), and Matérn cluster process (MCP). Subsequently, a 3D network model for THz-band Ultra-cell is demonstrated. Finally, we discuss major KPIs for 3D stochastic geometry and conclude with research challenges and open issues for 3D THz architectures.

Index Terms—3D; 6G; Stochastic geometry; URLLC; THz.

I. INTRODUCTION

The world is now embarking into the beyond fifth-generation (B5G) or sixth-generation (6G) Mobile Communications epoch [1], that will be wholly digital, enabling smartly enhanced mobile broadband connectivity and intelligent infrastructures to cater for the foreseen upsurge in mobile data. For example, it is expected that the total world traffic in mobile devices monthly will be about 164 ExaBytes (EB) in the year 2025¹, which is more than five times the traffic in the year 2019 (about 33 EB). Among various data traffic, the video will be predominant. The lion share of mobile traffic is already comprised of video traffic. For instance, in 2019, a significant portion of mobile traffic was video (63%), that is foreseen to increase in the coming years (e.g., the prediction is about 76% in 2025)². This trait will remain flourishing even after reaching the 5G milestone in 2020, with B5G/6G mobile networks expecting to hold up significantly higher capacity (throughput) per device (up to Terabits per second -Tbps).

Deployment of dense ultra-fast small cell technology is widely envisioned for enhancing the spectral and energy efficiency of 6G networks to meet the foreseen market demand. However, merely reducing the cell size within the current sub 6 GHz and millimeter-wave (mmWave) spectrum band

represents a short-term solution, where available spectral opportunities are limited and will certainly dry up. So, where do we look next? 6G research stakeholders are currently drilling for spectrum in the higher frequency bands, spurring the onset of Terahertz (THz) technologies [2], in an attempt to unlock vast swathes of the available spectrum representing a long-term solution to spectrum demand and entertaining the possibility of Tbps. Is the future 6G landscape only about a new spectrum?

Fig. 1. Evolution towards 6G (adapted from [1]).

United Nations urbanization study³ indicates that urban areas are projected to increase in population and density in large magnitude rapidly between now and 2050, with about two-thirds of Earth’s population, will be placed in urban areas by that time. This implies far-reaching and profound communication phenomenon, where more and more devices will be connected in complex, dense-urban environments such as the skyscrapers, high-rise infrastructures. In this context, the B5G/6G landscape aims to build on the initial 5G deployment phase (2020), envisioning an ultra-dense network of THz-based small cells (Ultra-cell) that goes beyond legacy two-dimensional (2D) deployment and aims to provide 5G services to skysrise buildings and high-altitude platforms. This will require mobile stakeholders to review the way current mobile networks are modeled and deployed for optimizing B5G/6G coverage. One of the methods is to model and deploy the mobile system in three-dimensional (3D) space.

Both THz and 3D architecture network modeling are touted as potential 6G enablers for the emerging mobile landscape [1], [3]. Table I presents a brief summary of 6G-enabling technology and architecture that includes THz and 3D network architecture.

A. Paper Contribution

This magazine paper provides a brief survey of 3D network modeling for THz frequency enabled Ultra-Fast dense

¹Ericsson AB, “Traffic Exploration Tool,” <http://www.ericsson.com/TET/trafficView/loadBasicEditor.ericsson>, accessed 03 December 2020.

²Ericsson Mobility Report – June 2020. <https://www.ericsson.com/en/mobility-report/reports/june-2020> accessed 03 December 2020.

³United Nations, “World urbanization prospects: The 2011 revision”, New York, 2012; <https://goo.gl/VBa3hN>

TABLE I
THE TRAIT OF THZ AND 3D NETWORK ARCHITECTURE AS 6G ENABLERS [1]

6G Enabling Technology	Potential	Challenges	Use cases
New spectrum→THz	Vast contiguous bandwidth, miniature antenna size, more focused beams	hardware design, propagation loss such as molecular absorption loss	Ubiquitous connectivity (MBRLLC), tactile telepresence (mURLLC), holographic (mURLLC), industry 4.0 (mURLLC)
Novel network architecture→3D network	Ubiquitous coverage in 3D space, uninterrupted service	Network modeling, optimization of topology, coverage probability, system efficiency such as energy efficiency	Ubiquitous connectivity (MBRLLC), digital healthcare system (mURLLC), mobility of unmanned devices (MBRLLC)
Mobile broadband reliable low-latency communication (MBRLLC [3]), massive ultra-reliable and low-latency communication (mURLLC [3]). These are 6G use cases envisioned in [3].			

networks from the upcoming 6G communication system's perspective, focusing on stochastic geometry analytical tool. This survey demonstrates and promotes attractive 6G scenarios, 3D network architectures, and the significance of stochastic geometry for network modeling. Moreover, it presents a comprehensive description of the different clustered process deployment while discussing 3D modeling for 6G THz Ultra-Cell. Several significant open issues are also highlighted for future research of the THz system.

B. Paper Organization

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The primer of 3D architecture and the 6G scenario is provided in Section II. Section III describes the mathematical tool—stochastic geometry—for network modeling and its relevant state-of-the-art (SoTA). The 3D network modeling technique for 6G THz-enabled Dense Ultra-Cell networks is discussed in Section IV. Primary performance metrics for stochastic Geometry based 3D network modeling are provided in Section V. Section VI highlights the research challenges and open issues while the conclusions follow in Section VII.

II. PRIMER OF 6G ULTRA-FAST SMALL CELL AND 3D NETWORK ARCHITECTURE

In this section, we describe two essential components of THz-based 3D network Modeling. Those are i) ultra-fast dense THz-enabled small cells (Ultra-cell), and ii) 3D network architecture.

A. Ultra-Fast THz-enabled Small Cells (Ultra-cells)

Amongst many, two primary criteria of 6G are i) more bits, more spectrum, more reliability, and ii) from 2D areal to 3D volumetric system efficiency—spectral and energy efficiency (SEE) [1], [3]. To satisfy those criteria of 6G require enormous data rates and diverse and distinctive network architecture than 5G, thus motivating further exploration in carrier frequencies above 6 GHz. The volumetric bandwidth definition of 6G will be increasingly associated with 3D network architectures than the 2D spatial (areal) network. This incorporates the advancement of sub-THz mmWave technologies (mobile mmWave) that will become established in initial 6G systems as an initial step. As the research exploration of 6G advances, utilizing

frequencies beyond mmWave will become necessary at the THz band. To make use of higher THz frequencies, the 6G cell size should reduce from small cells to “ultra-fast THz-enabled small cell (Ultra-cell)” whose radius is limited to only a few tens of meters [3]. This prompts novel architectural designs that require much denser deployments of ultra-cells. 6G ultra-fast tiny cells are deployed as indoor small cells in buildings, such as skyscrapers, office, school, home, etc. outdoors coexisting with macrocells. The base stations (BS) of the macrocell is termed as 5G next-generation NB (gNB). Unmanned aerial vehicle BS (UAV-BS) can be used as both standalone macro BS or small cell access point (AP). Fig. 2 demonstrates a potential 6G ultra-fast scenario with dense small cells.

B. 3D Network Architecture

Studies of cellular networks were mostly assuming unrealistic hypotheses such as 2D wireless networks. In fact, 2D models are tractable and very suitable for macro base stations (MBSs) in the terrain of rural or suburban landscapes. But, they are insufficient for dense urban areas, especially the small cells which are deployed in high-rise buildings, infrastructures, and so on. These models cannot describe the system specificities, mainly the actual distance between the BS and user equipment (UE). It is crucial to expound models with realistic constraints to improve the system model and gain from the accuracy of analytical expressions. 3D space modeling of cellular networks offers realistic and accurate system models. Therefore, the 3D network architecture is of fundamental importance to efficiently evaluate future mobile networks such as 6G.

Besides, previous generations including 5G, have been modeled and developed to cater for predominantly 2D space, i.e., network APs are deployed to provide connectivity and services to devices on the ground. Conversely, we envision future 6G heterogeneous network (HetNet) architectures to furnish 3D coverage, thereby accompanying terrestrial platforms with non-terrestrial infrastructures/devices, e.g., unmanned aerial vehicles or drones, and satellites. Thanks to incorporating non-terrestrial (air-borne) and terrestrial networks, communications in 3D space must be an integral part of 6G, including serving UEs in 3D and deploying 3D BS (e.g., UAV-BS→drones which can be used as also be used as temporary BS). 3D

Fig. 2. 6G Ultra-cell scenario in the physical domain.

Fig. 3. Top view of a 3D THz network architecture.

network modeling significantly varies from legacy 2D networks to a great extent thanks to the additional dimension (altitude/height) and the related degrees of freedom, and provides a platform for innovative system optimizations for mobility management, routing, and resource management [3].

Fig. 3 shows a top view of a 3D network architecture with the THz-enabled spectrum. The ground distance or the 2D distance between UE and transmitter is defined by the distance between the UE and the Ultra-cell transmitter's projection,

which is situated at the top of the building location onto the ground denoted by d_{2D} . The Euclidean distance or the 3D distance between UE and 3D transmitter is then presented by, $d_{3D} = \sqrt{d_{2D}^2 + a^2}$ where a is the altitude/elevation/height of the transmitter.

III. STOCHASTIC GEOMETRY TECHNIQUES FOR NETWORK MODELING: STATE-OF-THE-ART (SOTA))

Stochastic geometry is the primary mathematical tool that is widely used for communication systems modeling. Stochastic geometry is a branch of probability theory that can be used to describe the behavior of random configurations, such as random networks, random cluster processes, and so on. The stochastic geometry is proficient for studying wireless networks, since the coverage probability, interference, SINR distribution, and system capacity are sensitive to nodes' locations. It also offers, in most cases, expressions in closed-form for the spatial component of wireless systems. This section will highlight the SoTA of several types of stochastic geometry process that can be used for 3D THz wireless communication modeling. Stochastic geometry has already provided some viable evidence that Point Processes can indeed model so-called "repulsion and attraction" for transmitter deployments within a bounded space. However, current studies are limited towards conventional 2D space deployments, and there are no

clear models for characterizing very small THz-enabled cells. Until now, there are few studies that characterize 3D mobile deployment approaches in practical simulation environments let alone small cell (THz) deployment in 3D space for B5G/6G networks.

Urban network deployments are distinctively non-flat, yet the de facto approach from stochastic geometry treats all transmitters and receivers as placed on a 2D plane [4]. In stochastic geometry network models, tiers of base stations are modeled as independent point processes, mostly homogeneous Poisson Point Process (PPP) [5], the key benefits being mathematical tractability. However, a network model with a homogeneous distribution profile will show no spatial correlation between objects/points resulting in unrealistic models that deviate from practical network deployments. In fact, multi-tier networks offer both repulsion and attraction properties between points: small cell clustering shows properties of spatial attraction between transmitter points to represent coverage for user-centric hotspot areas, while macro cell coverage must show a degree of repulsion to minimize interference, in addition to being a more representative profile for rural environments. Stochastic geometry as a tool has been shown to cater for these specific instances, by resorting to non-PPP approaches. The Ginibre PP (GPP), under the umbrella of Determinantal point processes, can provide repulsion between nodes by varying the Beta function, that controls the degree of repulsion. It has been successfully applied to cellular networks in urban and rural environments [6], [7].

Clustered Point Processes (e.g., the Neyman-Scott process, Gaussian-Poisson Process, PCP) have been applied to model spatial coupling (attraction), making them suitable for modeling a high density of users accessing hotspot areas [8]–[10], achieving a good trade-off between modeling accuracy and tractability. [11] investigates the inhomogeneous Poisson point process (I-PPP), where the intensity function depends on distance leading to an interconnected, tractable, and feasible methodology for modeling cellular networks that exhibit both spatial clustering and/or repulsion. However, I-PPPs requires a definition for the distance-dependent intensity function, whose choice is challenging as no ‘a priori’ information on its structure exists up to now. Although stochastic geometry is a well-known statistical tool for modeling cellular networks; it is fairly unknown at present about the SINR distribution, coverage probability and rates achieved in dense urban deployments of cellular networks based on small cell technology at THz frequencies that are sensitive to blockages and exploit highly directional 3D beam patterns. Moreover, many of the spatial distribution principles of stochastic geometry extend to “3” dimensions [12]; but, their extension to urban areas is challenging because of the deployment of users and infrastructure in an inhomogeneously distributed manner.

IV. 3D NETWORK MODELING TECHNIQUE FOR 6G THZ-ENABLED DENSE ULTRA-CELL NETWORKS

Legacy mobile systems are modeled resorting to stochastic geometry that treats all transmitters and receivers as living on a 2D plane [4]. In this context, the Poisson Point Process

(PPP) is the most widely applied approach for modeling the deployment of a network deployment and derive the coverage probability, which holds a significant edge in terms of mathematical tractability. The PPP is a point process model where the number of transmitters (or access point(AP)) in a given area in 2D space or in a given volume in 3D space has a Poisson distribution with mean λ , where the parameter λ denotes the density of the APs per unit area for 2D or per unit volume for 3D. However, the PPP method assumes one fundamental and inherent basic premise in that the mathematical objects are distributed randomly in space.

However, actual typical networking models comprise multi-tier HetNets, where the BS models demonstrate different degrees of interactions among the locations in terms of repulsion and attraction: in small cell networks there tends to be attraction reflecting user-centric hotspot areas, whilst there will be repulsion noticed at the macro cell level to represent the deployments of rural/urban scenario. This distinction will be more stand out in ultra-dense tiny cell environments. In this context, it is pretty evident that the trusted PPP techniques will not represent a precisely B5G/6G networking environment, and until now restricted to the 2D plane. The interesting research question that arises is how to model a multitier deployment for the B5G/6G cellular environment, including the spatial dependencies for intra-tier small cell clustering in 3D space?

Poisson Voronoi (PV) [13] tessellation is very important for modeling 3D multitier networks integrating ultra-fast dense small cells. We define the PV cell by the edges labeling and differentiating the random coverage area of a given cell [14]. The probability density function (PDF) of the size of a 3D typical PV cell is calculated through the Monte Carlo method [13] and is given as follows [13], [14]:

$$f_Y(y) = \frac{5^5}{\Gamma(5)} y^4 \exp(-5y) \quad (1)$$

where Y is a discrete random variable that refers the magnitude of a regular PV cell that is normalized by the reciprocal of the dense ultra-cell density (λ), and $\Gamma(x) = \int_0^\infty \exp(-t)t^{x-1}$ is the gamma function [14].

In 3D stochastic geometry, a typical user is deployed where the properties of the spatial Poisson cluster process (PCP) can be computed. It provides the accuracy and the tractability of the network modeling. In other words, *the typical user is assumed to be a representative of all users. Most of the properties of a 3D wireless networking deployment can be expressed as a function of the distance between the THz Access Points (TAP) and the UE* [14]. Hence, the distance from the typical user to the nearest network nodes is of a special significance in the stochastic deployment modeling of wireless networks [14].

There are several PCP methods available to create 3D network modeling. Amongst all the PCP, two methods are standout, widely used, and easily tractable for deploying purposes. Those are Thomas Cluster Process (TCP) and Matérn Cluster Process (MCP) [10]. Fig. 4 presents the different PCP method and along with their distribution mechanism. These method works for homogeneous point process where we

assume the per unit volume density is not location dependent in a 3D scenario.

Fig. 4. Different types of cluster processes for 3D stochastic geometry [10].

Both TCP and MCP are stationary and isotropic PCP generated by a set of child points independently and identically distributed (i.i.d.) around each point of a parent PPP [9]. The only significant difference between these two PCP lies in the distribution of the child process, where MCP and TCP child points are uniformly distributed (in a ball) and symmetric Gaussian (Normal) distributed, respectively. Fig. 4 provides a graphical demonstration of these two PCPs for better understanding.

The 3D network model assumes a two-tier network that constitutes an underlaid macrocell network for the coverage of rural/urban environment and impromptu hotspot coverage zones of ultra-cells for capacity enhancement, which is aligned with the 3GPP model configuration for Heterogeneous networks [10] 3GPP stipulates a non-uniform distribution of users within the macro cell, and a correlated distribution of Ultra-cell small base station (UBS). 3D network modeling will model this configuration by a PCP, where the UBS locations are correlated and form spatial clusters according to the user hotspots for capacity-centric deployment.

Fig. 5. 3D Network model using 3D stochastic geometry PCP process.

Fig. 5 presents a 3GPP inspired network model which constitutes PCP. In this figure, the red triangle, the white square and the block dots denote Macro BSs, UBS and the users, respectively. For modeling such a networking scenario consists of UEs and UBS locations, we use two PCPs with a similar parent PPP with identically and independently distributed child point processes. That means UEs resemble the child process, and UBS resembles the parent process, respectively. Then

we model coupling for both the PCPs with the same parent PPP. Eventually, we evaluate and measure the sum-product functionals of PCPs and finite processes to characterize the downlink coverage probability under the maximum-SINR cell association. This phenomenon will be highly challenging at THz-band frequencies due to the penetration-sensitivity to different types of blockages, and the utilization of extremely directional 3D beam pattern.

V. MAJOR PERFORMANCE METRICS FOR STOCHASTIC GEOMETRY BASED 3D NETWORK MODELING

There are several key performance indicators (KPI) available to test and verify the results while deploying 3D stochastic geometry. In this section, we explain the two major KPIs which directly reflect and provide an accurate characterization in the modeling of the 3D THz Ultra-cell scenario [14]. These metrics are *primarily associated with either the signal to the interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) distribution that translates into ‘coverage/success probability’ or the ‘rate coverage’* [14].

Coverage/Success Probability: The coverage probability is determined as the probability that the SINR of a randomly selected UE is higher than a certain SINR threshold. In particular, this KPI tests whether the link quality is good enough for a successful connection. That is why the coverage probability is also termed as a success probability [14]. Conversely, it can also be defined as an outage probability where the distribution probability of the SINR falls below a minimum pre-defined threshold. Therefore, the outcome of the SINR distribution is a phenomenal characteristic to measure this KPI.

Rate Coverage: In Ultra-cell systems, rate coverage is specified as the probability that the obtainable rate of an arbitrary typical UE is above a certain threshold [14]. In ultra-cell, rate coverage and SINR distribution are interlinked. Moreover, SINR distribution in rate coverage is also used to characterize independent cells’ load, backhaul capacities, and energy efficiency.

VI. RESEARCH CHALLENGES AND OPEN ISSUES

There are a few research challenges and open issues need to be addressed for modeling 3D THz-band wireless system. In this section, we try to highlight those critical research challenges in brief.

A. 3D Channel modeling and optimization for THz bands

So far, very limited channel models are available for THz frequencies, especially for those higher than about 300 GHz or outdoor mobile scenarios. Since THz bands and mmWave bands share certain similarities, an extension of the 3GPP new channel model can be studied as a baseline. In addition, the research community might consider propagation modeling of THz networks in a quasi-static manner, a hybrid-model, i.e., a combination of stochastic and map-based models, to address THz channel characteristics. The major challenges lie in the presence of the users and base stations harnessing 3D channel modeling. Specific features such as blockage, molecular absorption, scattering and impact of different surface and

material need to be investigated on top of the hybrid model. Afterwards, the developed 3D channel models will need to be optimized for different THz-wave bands to support efficient initial access and beamforming/tracking using different frame structures and numerology. Moreover, novel 3D THz channel models are required, that relate the stochastic properties of the radio channel to the underlying geometry of the 3D network architecture. Moreover, Tbps rate baseband modulation and demodulation, and effective baseband algorithms also need to be investigated.

B. Novel Information-theoretical analysis for the 3D THz networks

5G waveforms (i.e., Filter Bank Multicarrier (FBMC), universal filtered multicarrier (UFMC), and generalized frequency division multiplexing (GFDM)) have the potential of inherent robustness against hardware impairments, reduction of signaling overhead, and good adaptability to mm-wave or microwave propagation characteristics, etc. However, for the higher THz band, the requirements on the hardware and channel propagation properties are different. Thus, a new waveform suitable for different THz mobile scenarios needs to be developed. Moreover, the researcher community need to find the novel theoretical capacity (the maximum achievable rates for single channels or network capacity) by informational-theoretical analysis of the various candidate spectrum bands with and without constraints (e.g., energy-efficiency, the nonlinearity of amplifier, ADC resolution and peak power, multiple antennas with or without CSI (Channel State Information)). Energy-efficiency in bits per Joules can be used to derive coherent and non-coherent channels by using information theory tools.

C. Mobility in 3D THz Networks

Mobility is perhaps the single most challenging and most daunting problem for 3D THz-based cellular networks, and the one most often raised by prominent skeptics. It is easy to understand why, in the context of the large beam steering gains needed to overcome the propagation losses. These gains require highly directional and/or adaptively tuned patterns that hold only for a small 3D angle in space. As the UE moves around, either it must rapidly switch beams or adapt the current beam. The feedback and latency requirements are very challenging. Mobility can be viewed as the cause of decorrelation. The mobility challenge lies in the large beam steering gains required to overcome the propagation losses at THz frequencies. These gains require highly directional and/or adaptively tuned patterns that hold only for a small 3D angle in space. In fact, the requirement for (nearly) unrestricted mobility is arguably the key feature of cellular networks. Therefore, the need to model and observe the impact of mobility is necessary to quantify mobile network performance and provide a basis for designing new algorithms/protocols. Therefore, in the first instance, a model is required to emulate user mobility in small cell deployment. Many such models have been proposed, but nearly all have significant drawbacks. They either provide reasonable accuracy or simplicity/tractability, but never both. Mobility support is mostly studied through

simulation studies, and cellular systems are still designed to support mobility primarily through iterative trial and error type approaches. Almost nothing is known about supporting mobility in THz networks since THz applications have been limited to personal/local area networks, or for line-of-sight (LoS) point-to-point communications. Furthermore, future emerging deployment scenarios will be 3D, adding another challenging dimension to the problem.

D. System-level Evaluation for B5G/6G networks

Simulations are pivotal for research and standardization. At this stage, although prototypes naturally deliver the most reliable results, they are typically not available, and testing different candidate features would be too expensive. In this context, exploiting a commercial system-level simulator to emulate and validate the analytical 3D network models for THz-based small cells is also an option. Simulations often rely on empirical models for characterizing the propagation channel. However, ray tracing can be used to plot the channel characteristics taking into account diverse physical phenomena including reflections, diffractions, and diffuse scattering for very specific channel environments, including 3D deployments. The initial step might be to use a commercial ray-tracing tool to implement new signal coverage maps, that will replace the baseline system-level simulation (SLS) channel models to provide enhanced simulation accuracy.

E. In-flight Broadband Connectivity

The advantages offered by the 6G communications will not only be restricted to terrestrial systems. In fact, several foreseen 6G scenarios and business cases extend towards the skies, where In-Flight Broadband connectivity (IFBC) will also become a commodity in the mid-long term. In fact, there were some 1.103 billion passengers served in 2018⁴, that traveled from and to European Union (EU) and the UK, making the in-flight broadband connectivity a real market opportunity. 6G systems are in the best position to harness this market, thanks to new design requirements to provide access to extreme geographical regions and ethos on digital inclusion to all. In this context, 6G aims to merge satellite communications with the terrestrial mobile system to deliver a converged 6G-Satellite connectivity platform capable of IFBC for the airline industry [15]. The system will harness advanced 5G NR technology to provide Direct-to-Air-Ground Communication (D2AGC) for guaranteeing an excellent quality of service (QoS), while using satellite components, like the low earth orbit (LEO) ones, for providing service at high altitudes. A 3D THz-band wireless ultra-fast small cell network will provide the in-cabin service. The system constitutes a hybrid connectivity platform that raises significant challenges in terms of delivering ultra-fast networks aligned with the 5G and 6G KPIs, and thus helping to overcome connectivity issues based on different regulatory frameworks across different countries

⁴Eurostat, "Air Transport Statistics" in Statistics Explained, December 2019. http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Air_%20transport_%20statistics, accessed 30 December 2020.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we provide a brief survey of 3D network modeling for the THz system including addressing key research challenges as we enter the 6G era. We discuss the new 6G Ultra-cell scenario along with the associated 3D network architecture. Several recent developments of network modeling applying a stochastic geometry-based clustered process are also presented. We also discuss several potential network modeling techniques such as Poisson Voronoi (PV) tessellation, Thomas cluster process (TCP), and Matérn cluster process (MCP). Subsequently, a 3D network model for THz-band Ultra-cell is demonstrated. Finally, we discuss major KPIs for 3D stochastic geometry and conclude with research challenges and open issues for 3D THz architectures.

VIII. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This project leading to this article has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 839573.

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BIOGRAPHY

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